

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Institutional assessment process checklist

Actionable version

Definition

This template is a structured tool to support research assessment processes at institutional level. The template is based on the Dutch Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) 2021–2027, as this approach may be useful beyond the Netherlands in helping research units, executive boards, and assessment committees document, coordinate, and follow up on key stages of an assessment. The focus is on evaluating a research unit against its own aims and strategy, while considering broader aspects such as research quality, societal relevance, viability, open science, academic culture, human resources policy, and PhD training.

Relevant SCOPE stages

The checklist is particularly useful in:

- Options for evaluating: structuring and clarifying how assessment will be organised.
- Probe deeply: ensuring thorough, transparent evaluation and reflection.

When and how to use

When:

- During planned research assessments (e.g. every 6 years, in line with SEP or equivalent national cycles).
- When developing or reviewing a unit's research strategy.
- To ensure alignment between organizational leadership, research units, and external assessment committees.

How:

- Familiarise yourself with the SEP protocol or your national equivalent.
- Convene all relevant actors (executive board, research unit leaders, impartial expert committee, secretary).
- Complete the template collaboratively, documenting: the unit's aims and strategy, strategic planning discussions, terms of reference and chosen indicators, duties and deliverables for each actor.
- Use the completed template to guide self-evaluation reports, site visits, committee reports, and board responses.
- Ensure outputs (self-evaluation, assessment reports, board responses) feed into the organisation's quality assurance cycle and are made public within six months.

Guidance

- For HR and research managers: Use the template to monitor whether diversity, open science, and career development aspects are fully embedded in assessment processes.
- For researchers and unit leaders: Provide evidence of achievements, a SWOT analysis, and forward-looking strategy, emphasising quality, societal impact, and viability.
- For executive boards: Ensure impartial committees are appointed, discussions are documented, and outcomes feed into institutional planning.
- For assessment committees: Reflect objectively on the unit's performance, covering both strategic aims and broader academic culture.

Practical tips:

- Treat the process as iterative and consultative, not purely administrative.

Further reading

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) 2021–2027 (VSNU, KNAW, NWO, 2020): https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/documents/SEP_2021-2027.pdf

